

SOURCES OF LOCAL BUDGET REVENUES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article devoted to open the topic sources of local budget revenues in Uzbekistan. Moreover, Statistical indicators of local budget revenues of Uzbekistan are also shown.

Key words: *budgetary funds, consolidated budget, Local Budget revenues, mandatory payments, Local taxes, budget expenditures.*

The budget system is a mix of central and local budgets controlled by the law, along with various taxes and fees. It also includes intergovernmental transfers of money based on economic relationships. It needs to be right for the type of government. The budget system means adding up the budgets of all levels in the country. Uzbekistan is a country that is controlled by one government. The budget system of Uzbekistan has two parts - the national budget and the local budgets. This is called a unitary state. These budgets are like a way to organize the government's money in a country. The state budget is a combination of the budget of the republican party, the budget of the Republic of Karakalpakstan (which is a self-governing region within Uzbekistan) and the budgets of different local areas. Right now, the government uses money from different funds to make the state budget. These funds and the state budget together become the consolidated budget. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Budget System” of 14 December 2000 establishes the legal basis for the functioning of the budgetary system and the budget system. According to this Law, “the budget system describes the budgets

and budget recipients at different levels, the principles of the organization and establishment of budgets, the relationship between them in the budget process”

The government's budget is the main part of its money plan. The government's spending plan will be made and used the way the law "On Budget System" and other laws say it should be. The Republic has a budget that helps pay for things that are run by the government. This budget shows where the money comes from and how much there is, as well as how much is needed for different things during the year. [1]. Local Budget revenues - These revenues are legally attributed to fully local budgets that is, local taxes and mandatory levies that form in this province or district. One of the major tasks that local financial bodies face today is to increase their share of their revenues in the total revenues of local budgets. As regional budgets increase their revenues, they become financially independent, reducing their dependence on higher budgets, for example, provincial or national budgets, and as a result, the national budget contributes to economic development, further development of the country and welfare of the population. Currently, according to Article 52 of the Budget Code, the following are the local budgets revenues:

a) Local taxes and other mandatory payments. Local taxes and fees - for the purpose of creating a source of social and economic development of the territory, reproduction of natural and other material resources, creation of necessary conditions for the functioning of state and local governments.

b) Non-refundable receipts from legal entities and individuals, as well as from foreign countries. These revenues include gifts in the form of gifts, gifts, as well as free donations.

c) Income from markets. Income from the various markets (dehkan markets, commodity markets, livestock markets, etc.) located in the respective administrative areas (one-time payments) are also included in local revenues.

d) Other income. Income from the sale of property transferred to the state, income from the placement, rent and sale of state assets according to the established norms, state duties, fees, indemnities and penalties to the budget of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, local budgets of provinces and Tashkent city, the property which is to be transferred to the state revenue under the right of inheritance revenues from sale and other incomes in accordance with the legislation. The importance of local taxes in the tax system is determined by their number and their role in total tax revenues. Local taxes are the primary source of income for local governments and their types are determined by the tax legislation of each country. Since the introduction of local taxes to the present day, changes in their structure have not only been quantitatively but also substantially. To date, new species have been introduced and are being effectively harvested. The share of local taxes in budget revenues should not be the only one that determines their role. In this regard, if one considers the role of local taxes in the formation of budget revenues, depending on the level of this indicator, such an assessment should be considered as an unreasonable estimate [2]. As international experience shows, the effectiveness of the system of budgetary revenues applied in the national economy of any country is not only characterized by the above indicator, but also depends on the organization of budget revenues.

The amount of money coming in is really important for planning how to spend money from the local budget. This is because expenses can only be paid if there is enough money to cover them. Expenses help bring in money for the local budget. The money that the employees of a budget organization pay in income taxes helps generate revenue for the budget. To do this, the budget must turn its revenues into expenses. This requires budget spending to go through a cycle, budget expenditures in the gross domestic product is presented in the section of the state budget and state special funds. From the image data, the period between 2015- 2019 can be divided into two. The first period covers the years 2015-2017,

and during this period, the share of budget expenditures, including the state budget and state trust fund expenditures, in relation to the GDP decreased. The second period includes 2018-2019. During this period, we can see that the share of budget expenses, in particular, state budget expenses compared to the gross domestic product, has increased sharply. Also, unlike the share of budget revenue in relation to GDP, the share of budget expenditure in relation to GDP is increasing. This is especially the case when the share of income in relation to the gross domestic product is increasing even during the period of 25%, which indicates that there is a deficit in the budget system[3].

The money used by the government in Uzbekistan and the budget they create are important to help make the economy better. The state budget is like the money jar that supports many important things the government does, like helping people, building things, making decisions, protecting the environment, and more. The budget is connected to all the money-related things the country does and there are rules to follow when deciding how to use the budget. Complete and effective implementation of the priorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan's development, sustainable and balanced economic development, robust place in world markets, ensuring consistent economic growth, enhancing the living standards and wellbeing of the people a thorough study of the mechanism of enforcement of the state budget is more timely than ever. We know that the budget revenues are the funds received in the budgetary system budget in the nondiscriminatory and non-repayable manner defined by the legislation. Budget revenues include tax and non-tax revenues. The revenue base of local budgets is directly linked to the national income generated in the regions, such as the level of development of production, the constant and regular revenue generation gains in the interest of local government revenue growth[4]. First of all, it is necessary to note that internal revenues of the local budget increase incomes, development of production in the regions, the privatization of state property in the implementation of economic

reforms, particularly in the field of economic reforms in the regions, the creation of various forms of ownership, development is crucial. Strengthening the revenue base of local budgets is directly related to the ongoing reforms in agriculture.

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